

Organizational Agility and Social Capital as Drivers of Resilience in the touristic SMEs: A Dynamic Capabilities Perspective

Agilité organisationnelle et capital social comme leviers de la résilience dans les PME touristiques : une perspective axée sur les capacités dynamiques

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Abstract

Organizational resilience is a growing concern in volatile sectors like tourism, especially in the wake of global crises such as COVID-19. While scholarly interest has increased, the influence of intangible resources on resilience in SMEs from emerging economies remains underexplored. This study examines how organizational agility and social capital shape the resilience of Moroccan tourism SMEs, focusing on the mediating role of dynamic capabilities. Anchored in the Dynamic Capabilities View and the Resource-Based View, the research uses PLS-SEM on data from 254 restaurant-sector SMEs in the Marrakech-Safi region. Findings reveal that agility boosts both social capital and resilience, with dynamic capabilities serving as mediators. Independent restaurants show greater adaptability. The study contributes to resilience theory in emerging contexts and offers practical guidance for SME managers.

Keywords: Organizational Resilience, Organizational Agility, Social Capital, Dynamic Capabilities

Résumé

La résilience organisationnelle est une préoccupation croissante dans les secteurs volatils comme le tourisme, en particulier à la suite de crises mondiales telles que la COVID-19. Bien que l'intérêt des chercheurs se soit accru, l'influence des ressources immatérielles sur la résilience des PME des économies émergentes reste sous-étudiée. Cette étude examine comment l'agilité organisationnelle et le capital social façonnent la résilience des PME touristiques marocaines, en se concentrant sur le rôle médiateur des capacités dynamiques.

Ancrée dans la théorie des capacités dynamiques et la théorie des ressources, cette recherche utilise la méthode PLS-SEM sur des données provenant de 254 PME du secteur de la restauration dans la région de Marrakech-Safi. Les résultats révèlent que l'agilité stimule à la fois le capital social et la résilience, les capacités dynamiques jouant un rôle de médiateurs. Les restaurants indépendants font preuve d'une plus grande adaptabilité. Cette étude contribue à la théorie de la résilience dans les contextes émergents et offre des conseils pratiques aux dirigeants de PME.

Mots clés : Résilience organisationnelle, agilité organisationnelle, capital social, capacités dynamiques

Introduction

In an era marked by recurrent global crises, including pandemics, geopolitical tensions, and climate-related disruptions, organizational resilience has become a central concern for firms seeking to sustain performance amid adversity. This issue is particularly critical for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating in high-risk sectors like tourism, where exposure to volatility is high and adaptive capacities are often limited. In Morocco, the COVID-19 crisis severely impacted tourism-related SMEs, revealing not only financial weaknesses but also deeper structural and institutional vulnerabilities. Identifying resilience factors in such contexts is thus both timely and necessary.

Although the body of research on organizational resilience has grown, important gaps remain, particularly concerning its antecedents in SMEs from developing economies and shock-sensitive sectors. While tangible resources and structural preparedness have been widely studied, there is a relative lack of attention to intangible assets, such as organizational agility (OA) and social capital (SC), and how these enable firms to absorb, adapt to, and recover from crises. The mediating role of dynamic capabilities (DC) in this process remains especially under-theorized, notably in North African contexts where SMEs are vital yet face persistent systemic risks (Ahachmi & al., 2025).

This study addresses these gaps by investigating how OA and SC influence organizational resilience (OR) among Moroccan tourism SMEs, with a focus on the mediating effect of dynamic capabilities. The central research question asks: *To what extent do organizational agility and social capital enhance resilience in tourism SMEs, and how is this relationship mediated by dynamic capabilities?*

The theoretical framework combines the Dynamic Capabilities Theory (Teece, 2007), the Resource-Based View (Barney, 1991), and Social Capital Theory (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998). It posits that internal and relational intangible resources only foster resilience when strategically mobilized through processes of learning, adaptation, and renewal.

Methodologically, the study uses a quantitative approach based on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Data were collected from SMEs in the restaurant segment of Morocco's tourism sector, enabling empirical validation of the conceptual model linking OA, SC, DC, and OR. The article proceeds with a detailed presentation of the theoretical framework and hypotheses, followed by the methodology, results, discussion, and implications, concluding with the study's limitations and suggestions for future research.

1. Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses Development

1.1. Organizational Resilience in SMEs and the Tourism Sector

Organizational resilience, initially defined as the ability to function under adverse conditions (Mallak, 1998), has evolved into a multidimensional, proactive capability. Weick (1993, 2003) emphasized its social and cognitive roots, while Duchek (2020) framed it as a dynamic process involving anticipation, coping, and adaptation. This view links resilience to learning, innovation, and strategic transformation. It is thus seen as a systemic response rather than an individual trait.

In tourism SMEs, resilience is vital due to resource constraints and vulnerability to shocks. Despite these limits, their agility and local stakeholder ties support adaptive responses. Empirical studies highlight internal drivers (leadership, coordination) and external ones (social capital, client trust) as key enablers. Overall, resilience appears as a composite capability enabling continuity and value creation in turbulent contexts (Ahachmi & al., 2025).

Tableau 1: Definitions of Organizational Resilience in Tourism SMEs

Authors	Definitions of Organizational Resilience in Tourism SMEs
Núñez-Ríos et al. (2021)	<i>Organizational resilience refers to the internal components (intelligence, training, management) that enable tourism SMEs to anticipate, absorb, and adapt to crises, enhancing continuity.</i>
Suherman et al. (2024)	<i>Defined as the ability of tourism-based SMEs to absorb shocks and thrive post-crisis through relational capital, innovation frugality, and ambidexterity, based on a resource-based view.</i>
Zhao & Li (2023)	<i>Organizational resilience is viewed as a systemic response to environmental pressures, shaped by configurations of firm state, response mechanisms, and structural conditions.</i>
Badoc-Gonzales et al. (2022)	<i>Resilience is understood as the capacity of SMEs to withstand and adapt to external disruptions while sustaining the destination ecosystem.</i>
Chhatwani & Mishra (2022)	<i>Defined as the ability of tourism SMEs to recover from failure through leadership, transparent communication, and organizational learning.</i>
Fostering Employee Resilience (2023)	<i>Describes resilience as the organizational and employee-level capacity to respond constructively to disruptions, recover operationally, and build adaptive capabilities in tourism firms.</i>

Source : Authors

1.2. Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCV)

1.2.1. Dynamic Capabilities as a Lever of Resilience in SMEs

The Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV) builds on the Resource-Based View (RBV), addressing its static limitations by focusing on how firms adapt in dynamic environments (Barney, 1991; Teece et al., 1997). While RBV emphasizes owning VRIN resources, DCV stresses the ability

to reconfigure and renew resources. Teece (2007, 2012, 2022) outlines three core processes, sensing, seizing, and transforming, as essential for strategic agility and resilience (Ahachmi & al., 2024).

In volatile sectors like tourism, dynamic capabilities are vital for SMEs to respond and recover effectively. These higher-order routines support learning, flexibility, and real-time model adaptation (Barreto, 2010; Wang & Ahmed, 2007). Empirical evidence confirms their impact: tourism SMEs use ambidexterity and frugal innovation to sustain operations (Suherman et al., 2024), while sensing and reconfiguring capabilities enhance adaptive performance (Zhao & Li, 2023). Combined with social capital and agility, dynamic capabilities promote both resilience and long-term renewal

1.2.2. Organizational Agility as a Dynamic Capability

Organizational agility, rooted in the dynamic capabilities framework (Teece, 2007), reflects a firm’s ability to sense change, seize opportunities, and reconfigure internal processes to maintain competitiveness (Overby et al., 2006; Doz & Kosonen, 2008). Unlike operational flexibility, it involves deeper strategic transformation, learning, and integration across functions (Appelbaum et al., 2017; Ahachmi & al., 2024). Agility is commonly described through dimensions such as environmental sensing, responsiveness, and continuous strategic alignment. The table 2 below presents a selection of key definitions from the literature.

Tableau 2 : Definitions of Organizational Agility

Authors	Definition of Organizational Agility
Goldman, Nagel & Preiss (1995)	<i>The ability of an enterprise to thrive in a continuously changing, unpredictable business environment by responding quickly and effectively to change.</i>
Doz & Kosonen (2008)	<i>The capability to continuously adjust and renew the organization’s strategic direction, business system, and organizational structure to create value.</i>
Overby, Bharadwaj & Sambamurthy (2006)	<i>The ability to sense environmental change and respond readily through innovative resource deployment and business process reconfiguration.</i>
Tallon & Pinsonneault (2011)	<i>The firm’s ability to detect and respond to opportunities and threats with speed and effectiveness.</i>
Appelbaum et al. (2017)	<i>The capacity to rapidly and effectively reconfigure business processes, structures, and strategies in response to changes in the environment.</i>

Source : Authors

▪ **Theoretical Link: Agility and Resilience in Tourism SMEs**

In tourism SMEs, organizational agility is a key driver of resilience, enabling firms to detect change, respond quickly, and reconfigure operations to maintain continuity amid disruption. It fosters strategic flexibility, decentralized decision-making, and proactive adaptation, critical traits for survival in volatile environments. Empirical studies confirm that agile SMEs recover more effectively post-crisis by sustaining innovation, stakeholder responsiveness, and operational coherence (Zhao & Li, 2023; Suherman et al., 2024). Thus, agility emerges not only as a reactive response but as a strategic, resilience-building capability grounded in continuous sensing and transformation.. Accordingly, this research advances the following hypothesis:

H1. Organizational agility positively influences organizational resilience in tourism SMEs.

▪ **Agility as an Antecedent of Dynamic Capabilities and Social Capital**

Organizational agility acts as a meta-capability that supports the development of dynamic capabilities by fostering foundational routines such as strategic scanning, learning, and leadership alignment (Teece, 2012; Wang & Ho, 2020). It enhances adaptive behavior and real-time resource reconfiguration, particularly in resource-constrained tourism SMEs (Mikalef & Pateli, 2017). Simultaneously, agility strengthens social capital by promoting internal trust, collaboration, and shared goals, while also facilitating external stakeholder engagement and flexible partnerships (Tsai & Ghoshal, 1998; Kwon & Adler, 2014). Together, these mechanisms position agility as a catalyst for dynamic renewal and relational strength, leading to the formulation of two key hypotheses regarding its influence on dynamic capabilities and social capital. Accordingly, this study formulates the following hypotheses:

H3. Organizational agility positively influences social capital in tourism SMEs.

1.3. Social Capital as an Intangible Resource of Resilience

Social capital (SC) is a strategic intangible asset that enhances organizational adaptability in complex, uncertain environments. Rooted in the works of Bourdieu (1986), Coleman (1988), and Putnam (1995), SC encompasses the trust, norms, and shared understandings embedded in social networks that facilitate coordination. Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) conceptualize it through structural, relational, and cognitive dimensions, which together foster communication, cohesion, and strategic alignment. As Adler and Kwon (2002) emphasize, the value of SC lies

in relationship quality, positioning it as a key systemic driver of resilience. The table 3 below presents a selection of key definitions from the literature.

Tableau 3 : Definitions of Social Capital

Authors	Definition of Social Capital
Bourdieu (1986)	<i>The aggregate of actual or potential resources linked to the possession of a durable network of institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance and recognition.</i>
Coleman (1988)	<i>A variety of different entities with two common elements: embedded in social structure, and facilitating certain actions of individuals.</i>
Putnam (1995)	<i>Features of social organization, such as networks, norms, and trust, that facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit.</i>
Nahapiet & Ghoshal (1998)	<i>The sum of the actual and potential resources embedded within, available through, and derived from the network of relationships possessed by an individual or unit.</i>
Adler & Kwon (2002)	<i>The goodwill available to individuals or groups, stemming from social relations and producing benefits through information, influence, and solidarity.</i>
Tsai & Ghoshal (1998)	<i>A multidimensional concept composed of structural (ties), relational (trust), and cognitive (shared vision) dimensions of intra- and inter-organizational networks.</i>

Source : Authors

In tourism SMEs, social capital (SC) enhances resilience both internally and externally. Internally, it fosters trust, communication, and team cohesion, supporting coordinated action and emotional stability during crises. Externally, SC builds enduring ties with stakeholders, customers, suppliers, institutions, that facilitate information flow, partnerships, and adaptive support (Ozanne et al., 2022; Markovic et al., 2021; Ahachmi & al., 2025). While some authors distinguish internal from external SC, recent perspectives view it holistically as a unified capability that reinforces both internal coordination and external adaptability (Kwon & Adler, 2014), positioning SC as a core enabler of resilience in turbulent environments. Drawing on these theoretical and empirical insights, the following hypothese is advanced

H4. Social capital positively influences organizational resilience in tourism SMEs.

1.4. The Mediating Role of Dynamic Capabilities

Dynamic capabilities (DCs) are increasingly viewed not only as strategic assets but as mechanisms that transform resources like agility and social capital into higher-order outcomes such as resilience (Teece, 2007; Wang & Ahmed, 2007). In volatile environments, possessing valuable resources is insufficient unless firms can reconfigure and redeploy them effectively. DCs thus serve as enabling infrastructures that convert sensing and relational potential into timely, effective action (Teece, 2012; Barreto, 2010; Ahachmi & al., 2025). Empirical studies support this mediating role. Suherman et al. (2024) show that agility contributes to resilience

primarily through dynamic capabilities like strategic sensing and model adaptation. Similarly, Zhao and Li (2023) argue that while social capital grants access to information and support, its impact on adaptability depends on a firm’s ability to absorb and act on this input via DCs. In this view, DCs act as a bridge between latent potential and realized resilience. Based on these insights, we propose the following hypotheses:

H5. Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between organizational agility and organizational resilience in tourism SMEs.

H6. Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between social capital and organizational resilience in tourism SMEs.

The conceptual model developed in this study integrates the Dynamic Capabilities View (DCV), social capital theory, and agility literature to explain resilience in tourism SMEs. It posits that agility and social capital are critical intangible antecedents of resilience, but their effects are mediated by dynamic capabilities, namely, the sensing, seizing, and transforming functions essential to adaptation (Teece, 2007).

By positioning DCs as the core mechanism linking resources to resilience, the model offers a comprehensive, process-oriented understanding of how tourism SMEs can build resilience through strategic mobilization of internal and external capacities. The figure 1 below present our research model.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Source : Authors

2. Method

2.1. Study context

2.1.1. Touristic Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) definitions

SMEs are vital for economic development and employment, though their definitions vary by country based on size, turnover, and organizational structure (Rutashobya & Olomi, 1999). The EU sets the threshold at 250 employees, while the U.S. and Canada use 499. In Morocco, Maroc PME defines SMEs as having 10–200 employees, turnover under 75 million MAD, or assets below 50 million MAD. In tourism, SMEs include small hotels, restaurants, and travel agencies, key players in the value chain but highly vulnerable to external shocks due to their limited resources. The table 4 below outlines key definitional criteria for tourism SMEs across contexts.

Tableau 4: key definitional criteria for tourism SMEs

Tourism Activity	Definition Criteria	References
Hotels	Classified as 1- to 3-star hotels or fewer than 50 rooms; staff below 50 employees.	WTO (2001), UNWTO, Moroccan Ministry of Tourism
Guesthouses / Riads	Fewer than 20 rooms, family-run structure, minimal staff, strong local anchoring.	CRT Marrakech (2022)
Tourist Restaurants	Capacity under 120 seats, annual turnover < 5 million MAD, staff below 20.	National Restaurant Federation (FNR), Morocco SME Agency (2021)
Travel Agencies	Fewer than 10 employees, annual turnover < 10 million MAD, regional or national-level operations.	Moroccan Agency for Tourism Development (SMIT)
Tourist Transport	Fleet under 10 vehicles, staff < 20, highly seasonal activity dependent on tourist flows.	National Office for Transport (ONMT), AMRC Sectoral Report (2020)
Leisure Service Providers	Staff < 50, independent management, offering experiential products (excursions, cultural, sports).	OECD Tourism Trends (2019)

Source: Authors

2.1.2. Sample and data

This study uses a quantitative, causal design to explore the relationship between dynamic managerial capabilities and organizational resilience in Marrakech-Safi’s restaurant sector. Data¹ were collected from various restaurant types between September 2024 and January 2025, focusing on post-crisis practices in knowledge management, innovation, and adaptability. A simple random sampling method yielded 254 valid responses. To test the proposed model, PLS-SEM was conducted using SmartPLS 4. Sample adequacy was confirmed using Grais’ formula

¹ **Methodological note:** The data in this study comes from self-administered statements by respondents. This method, which is common in management research, may have certain limitations, although precautions have been taken to mitigate bias.

(minimum = 196) and G*Power analysis (minimum = 175), with the final sample exceeding both thresholds.

2.2. Measures

Given the focus on SMEs in the restaurant sector, the study employed a cross-sectional survey design, utilizing a single key informant from each participating organization. All constructs were measured using multi-item reflective indicators rated on 7-point Likert scales ($1 = \text{“strongly disagree”}$ to $7 = \text{“strongly agree”}$), as summarized in Table 5 and detailed in Appendix B. For the measurement of social capital, respondents were instructed to evaluate their relationships with key external stakeholders, including customers and suppliers.

Several control variables were incorporated across individual, organizational, and industry levels. At the individual level, the respondents' educational background and professional experience were considered. Organizational-level controls included firm size and age. Given the cross-sectional nature of the study and the sector's heterogeneity, sub-sector distinctions, such as independent restaurants, hotel-based dining establishments, and fast-food outlets, were also introduced as industry-level control variables.

Table 5: Overview of construct measures

Construct	Items	Source
Organizational Agility (OA)	6	Tallon & Pinsonneault (2011); Overby et al. (2006); Doz & Kosonen (2008); Appelbaum et al. (2017)
Social Capital (SC)	10	Carey, Lawson & Krause (2011); Chowdhury et al. (2020); Villena et al. (2011); Ozanne et al. (2022)
Dynamic Capabilities (DC)	15	Mikalef & Pateli (2017); Pavlou & El Sawy (2011); Wilden et al. (2013)
Organizational Resilience (OR)	12	Bode & Macdonald (2017); Pettit et al. (2013); Jia et al. (2020); Ozanne et al. (2022)

Source : Authors

3. Results

The study began with a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using Varimax rotation, identifying three latent components with strong loadings, limited cross-loadings, and acceptable internal consistency, in line with standard guidelines (Hair et al., 2019; Sarstedt et al., 2022). A subsequent Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) using SPSS confirmed the construct structure, with fit indices (CFI, TLI, RMSEA) meeting recommended thresholds (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

For hypothesis testing, Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was used via SmartPLS 4, due to its suitability for exploratory research, tolerance for non-normal data, and efficiency with moderate samples (Hair et al., 2021). PLS-SEM allowed integrated

assessment of measurement and structural models, ensuring reliability, validity, and robust estimation of mediation and higher-order effects.

3.1. Statistics descriptives

Table 6 summarizes the sample’s descriptive statistics. A majority of respondents are based in Marrakech (55.9%), confirming the city’s touristic and economic dominance in the region, followed by Essaouira (14.2%) and Safi (9.4%). Independent restaurants constitute the largest group (46.5%), reflecting a vibrant entrepreneurial base, while hotel-based (33.9%) and fast-food establishments (19.7%) show diversification within the sector. Most respondents are male (63.4%) and hold senior roles, owners or managers, highlighting direct involvement in operational decisions.

Sociodemographic data reveal that the 35-44 age group is most represented (34.3%), followed by 45-54 (24%), indicating an experienced managerial profile. Educational levels are relatively high, with over 68% holding university or vocational degrees, pointing to increasing professionalization in the sector. The low presence of individuals under 25 (4.7%) and those without formal education (2.4%) reinforces this trend.

Tableau 6: Statistics descriptives

Category	Sub-category	Nbre	%	Category	Sub-category	Nbre	%
City (Location)	Marrakech	142	55.9%	Age of Respondents	18 to 25 years	12	4.7%
	Essaouira	36	14.2%		26 to 34 years	58	22.8%
	Safi	24	9.4%		35 to 44 years	87	34.3%
	Kalaa Sraghna	13	5.1%		45 to 54 years	61	24.0%
	Benguerir	10	3.9%		55 to 64 years	29	11.4%
	Aït Ourir	8	3.1%		65 and above	7	2.8%
	Tahannaout	7	2.8%		Position in the Firm	Owner	102
	Amez Miz	5	2.0%	Senior		76	29.9%
	Chichawa	5	2.0%	Head Chef		33	13.0%
	Chemaia	4	1.6%	Co-owner		21	8.3%
Type of Establishment	Independent restaurant	118	46.5%	Other	22	8.6%	
	Hotel-based restaurant	86	33.9%	Level of Education	No formal education	6	2.4%
	Fast-food restaurant	50	19.7%		Primary education	19	7.5%
Gender	Male	161	63.4%		Secondary (high school)	46	18.1%
					Certificate	73	28.7%
	Female	92	36.6%		University undergraduate	65	25.6%
					Graduate	35	13.8%
				Other qualification	10	3.9%	

Source : Authors

3.2. Common method bias

To mitigate the risk of common method bias (CMB), the study adopted both procedural and statistical remedies in line with best practices (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The questionnaire was developed with input from academic experts in resilience and social capital and was pilot tested to ensure clarity and content validity. Data were collected from well-informed respondents, owners, founders, or senior managers, most familiar with the firm's activities. To reduce priming effects, independent and dependent variables were placed in distinct sections of the instrument, and respondent anonymity was guaranteed.

Statistically, Harman's single-factor test revealed that no single factor accounted for more than 41.8% of the total variance, remaining below the 50% threshold (Podsakoff & Organ, 1986). Additionally, using the unmeasured latent method construct technique (Liang et al., 2007), the average variance explained by substantive constructs was 0.622, while method-based variance averaged 0.009. Finally, collinearity was assessed via full VIF values, all of which ranged from 1.025 to 2.914, staying well below the 3.30 cutoff (Kock, 2015). These combined controls confirm that the results are not significantly affected by common method bias.

3.3. Evaluation of measurement model

The reliability and convergent validity of the measurement model were assessed following recommended procedures (Hair et al., 2017; Sarstedt et al., 2019). All items demonstrated strong and statistically significant loadings ($p < 0.001$), confirming their association with the intended latent constructs. Internal consistency was confirmed, with Cronbach's alpha (α), composite reliability (CR), and Rho_A (ρ_A) values all exceeding the 0.70 threshold (Hair et al., 2021). Convergent validity was further supported by Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values above 0.50 for all constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), indicating that each latent variable accounted for sufficient variance in its indicators.

Discriminant validity was established through the Fornell–Larcker criterion and the Heterotrait–Monotrait ratio (HTMT). In all cases, the square root of each construct's AVE exceeded its correlations with other constructs, and HTMT values remained below the conservative threshold of 0.85 (Henseler, Hubona, & Ray, 2016). All constructs were modeled as higher-order reflective–reflective structures using the two-stage approach (Sarstedt et al., 2019). Following the validation of first-order constructs, latent variable scores were used to

estimate second-order constructs, which also met acceptable levels of reliability and validity (see tables 6 and 10 in the appendixes).

3.4. Evaluation of structural model

To test the conceptual model, Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was conducted using SmartPLS 4. This method was selected for its suitability with small samples, complex models, and non-normal data (Hair et al., 2021; Sarstedt et al., 2022). A bootstrapping procedure with 5,000 subsamples assessed path significance. Following Anderson and Gerbing’s (1988) two-stage approach, the measurement model was first evaluated using indicators such as item loadings, Cronbach’s alpha, rho_A, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE), following standard thresholds (Hair et al., 2019; Shiau & Chau, 2021).

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) using SPSS confirmed the factor structure, with KMO values > 0.60 (Field, 2018). Reliability was supported by Cronbach’s alpha values > 0.70 (Nunnally & Bernstein, 2019). SmartPLS results confirmed convergent validity (loadings > 0.70, AVE > 0.50) and discriminant validity via the Fornell–Larcker criterion and HTMT ratios < 0.85 (Henseler et al., 2015). These results validate the measurement model for structural analysis.

Tableau 7 : Correlation matrix for all sample

Construct	OA	SC	DC	OR	SIZE	AGE
OA	0,823	0,532	0,513	0,666	0.691	0.706
SC	0,784***	0,893	0,523	0,506	0.702	0.609
DC	0,748**	0,752***	0,885	0,635	0.502	0.710
OR	0,711***	0,734**	0,871**	0,901	0.617	0.652
SIZE	0.662**	0.418***	0.542***	0.610***	0.853	0.724
AGE	0.652***	0.513***	0.498**	0.517**	0.511***	0.824

Bolded values on the diagonal are the square root of the AVE, below the diagonal is the Fornell & Larcker value | *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 | OA : Organizational Agility; DC : Dynamic Capability; SC : Social Capital; OR : Organizational resilience

Source : Authors

Table 7 provides strong support for the discriminant validity of the model constructs, in line with the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion. For each construct, the square root of the AVE (displayed on the diagonal) exceeds its highest correlation with any other construct, confirming that each latent variable captures a unique conceptual domain. For example, the square root of the AVE for Organizational Resilience (0.901) is higher than its strongest correlation with Dynamic Capability (0.871), while Organizational Agility (0.823) exceeds its correlation with

Social Capital (0.784). These results validate the distinctiveness of the constructs and reinforce the robustness of the measurement model.

Beyond methodological validation, the inter-construct correlations reveal theoretically coherent associations. Organizational Agility shows strong and significant correlations with Social Capital ($r = 0.784$, $p < 0.01$) and Organizational Resilience ($r = 0.711$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that agility contributes to both social embeddedness and adaptive capacity. Dynamic Capability also emerges as a central construct, strongly correlated with both Resilience ($r = 0.871$) and Social Capital ($r = 0.752$), highlighting its pivotal role in the organizational response to environmental disruptions. While firm size and age exhibit moderate correlations with the core constructs, their AVE values remain sufficiently high to confirm their discriminant validity, supporting their relevance as control variables without undermining the model's conceptual integrity.

Tableau 8: Validity and reliability

Construct	Item loading	rho_A	AVE	CR	VIF	α
OA	0,656	0,665	0,643	0,931	1,415	0,797
SC	0,697	0,679	0,679	0,939	1,365	0,907
DC	0,699	0,765	0,716	0,901	1,367	0,793
OR	0,605	0,655	0,659	0,949	1,999	0,776
SIZE	0,695	0,797	0,714	0,956	1,407	0,915
AGE	0,614	0,661	0,655	0,961	1,361	0,794

OA : Organizational Agility; DC : Dynamic Capability; SC : Social Capital; OR : Organizational resilience

Source : Authors

Table 8 presents the reliability and validity indicators for each construct in the model. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for all constructs exceeds the recommended threshold of 0.50 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), confirming acceptable convergent validity. Specifically, AVE values range from 0.643 (Organizational Agility) to 0.716 (Dynamic Capability), indicating that each construct captures a substantial proportion of variance from its indicators. Additionally, the Composite Reliability (CR) values are all above 0.90, reflecting strong internal consistency across constructs. For instance, the CR values for SC (0.939), OR (0.949), and SIZE (0.956) demonstrate high measurement precision.

The Cronbach's alpha (α) coefficients, ranging from 0.776 to 0.915, further support the internal reliability of the measurement model. Moreover, rho_A values, considered a more accurate estimator of construct reliability, are also within acceptable bounds for all constructs. While item loadings are slightly below the optimal threshold of 0.70 for certain constructs (OR at

0.605 and OA at 0.656), these values remain acceptable given the strong CR and AVE levels. The Variance Inflation Factors (VIF), all below the conventional cut-off of 5, indicate the absence of multicollinearity concerns. The highest VIF (1.999 for OR) warrants monitoring but does not compromise the overall validity of the model. Collectively, these indicators confirm that the measurement model demonstrates satisfactory reliability, convergent validity, and low multicollinearity, supporting its use in subsequent structural analyses.

Tableau 9: Estimation results for hypotheses

Paths		β	t-stats	p-values
Direct Effect				
	OA → SC	0,784	29,568	0,000
	OA → DC	0,161	14,983	0,003
	OA → OR	0,161	2,983	0,005
	SC → DC	0,053	5,001	0,002
	SC → OR	0,053	3,604	0,005
Indirect Effect				
	OA → DC → OR	0,285	5,904	0,004
	SC → DC → OR	0,255	5,575	0,003
Control				
Industry	Independent restaurant → DC	0,178	4,394	0,003
	Hotel-based restaurant → DC	0,007	0,13	0,016
	Fast-food restaurant → DC	0,038	0,877	0,368
	Age → DC	0,021	0,818	0,413
	Size → DC	0,089	2,931	0,003
Industry	Independent restaurant → OR	0,203	2,054	0,005
	Hotel-based restaurant → OR	-0,035	2,963	0,002
	Fast-food restaurant → DC	0,012	0,374	0,738
	Age → OR	-0,002	0,073	0,941
	Size → OR	0,044	1,821	0,069

OA : Organizational Agility; DC : Dynamic Capability; SC : Social Capital; OR : Organizational resilience

Source : Authors

The structural model estimation yields strong empirical support for most of the hypothesized relationships, see table 9. Among the direct effects, Organizational Agility (OA) has a highly significant and substantial positive influence on Social Capital (SC) ($\beta = 0.784$, $t = 29.568$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that agile organizations tend to foster stronger social networks and collaborative structures. OA also shows significant direct effects on Dynamic Capability (DC) ($\beta = 0.161$, $t = 14.983$, $p = 0.003$) and Organizational Resilience (OR) ($\beta = 0.161$, $t = 2.983$, $p = 0.005$), supporting the idea that agility enhances both adaptive capabilities and resilience to disruptions. SC, in turn, positively affects both DC ($\beta = 0.053$, $t = 5.001$, $p = 0.002$) and OR (β

= 0.053, $t = 3.604$, $p = 0.005$), although the effect sizes are smaller, suggesting a complementary role in capability and resilience development.

Regarding the indirect effects, the mediation paths are both significant and meaningful. The path from OA to OR through DC is supported ($\beta = 0.285$, $t = 5.904$, $p = 0.004$), as is the path from SC to OR via DC ($\beta = 0.255$, $t = 5.575$, $p = 0.003$). These findings highlight the mediating role of Dynamic Capability in translating both agility and social capital into organizational resilience.

In terms of control variables, the industry type has differentiated effects. Being an independent restaurant is positively associated with both DC ($\beta = 0.178$, $t = 4.394$, $p = 0.003$) and OR ($\beta = 0.203$, $t = 2.054$, $p = 0.005$), suggesting greater adaptability and resilience outside formal hotel structures. Conversely, hotel-based restaurants show a negative effect on OR ($\beta = -0.035$, $t = 2.963$, $p = 0.002$), which may reflect structural rigidity or lower autonomy in crisis response. Firm size positively influences DC ($\beta = 0.089$, $t = 2.931$, $p = 0.003$) and marginally affects OR ($\beta = 0.044$, $t = 1.821$, $p = 0.069$), while firm age does not exhibit any significant effect on either outcome. These results confirm the importance of organizational and contextual factors in shaping dynamic and resilient behaviors in the hospitality sector.

4. Discussion

The substantial direct effect of Organizational Agility (OA) on Social Capital (SC) ($\beta = 0.784$, $p < 0.001$) confirms the foundational role agility plays in nurturing relational cohesion both within and beyond organizational boundaries. Agility enables firms to rapidly detect changes and respond with strategic intent, thereby strengthening the quality and frequency of interactions among stakeholders, a mechanism that underpins trust, shared norms, and mutual understanding (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998; Doz & Kosonen, 2008). In the context of Moroccan tourism SMEs. These findings echo Polyviou et al. (2020), who assert that agile firms can embed social capital into operational routines, particularly through decentralized leadership and stakeholder proximity. Given the high relational density of the Moroccan tourism ecosystem, characterized by localized supply chains, informal partnerships, and cultural embeddedness, agility emerges not only as a performance enhancer but as a strategic precursor to social infrastructure resilience. In this light, our results suggest that agile SMEs are uniquely positioned to mobilize and sustain social capital in volatile contexts, ultimately reinforcing adaptive capacity.

The results provide robust empirical support for the mediating role of Dynamic Capabilities (DC) in translating OA and SC into Organizational Resilience (OR). The indirect effects observed (OA → DC → OR: $\beta = 0.285$; SC → DC → OR: $\beta = 0.255$) emphasize that while agility and social capital are essential antecedents, their impact on resilience becomes significantly more potent when processed through dynamic capabilities. This aligns with Teece's (2007, 2012) framework, wherein DCs are conceptualized as higher-order routines enabling firms to sense, seize, and transform resources in response to environmental turbulence. In the Moroccan context, Ahachmi and Lahfidi (2024) show that tourism SMEs with strong sensing and adaptation capabilities were better equipped to survive COVID-19 disruptions, thanks to their ability to reconfigure internal processes and maintain continuity. Similarly, findings from the North Africa Resilience Observatory (2025) highlight that DCs serve as key mechanisms for transforming relational and structural capital into operational resilience under crisis conditions. These insights confirm the pivotal role of DCs as a bridge between intangible resources and tangible organizational outcomes, positioning them as the core drivers of long-term resilience strategies in emerging-market SMEs.

Although the indirect pathways through DC dominate the model, the direct effects of OA on DC ($\beta = 0.161$, $p = 0.003$) and OR ($\beta = 0.161$, $p = 0.005$) remain statistically significant. These relationships reinforce the dual role of agility as both a strategic trigger and an independent lever of resilience. Agility equips SMEs with the cognitive and operational flexibility to realign resources in real time, bypassing procedural rigidity and enabling rapid responses to shocks. This resonates with Eisenhardt and Martin (2000), who argue that agile routines may themselves constitute dynamic capabilities in moderately volatile environments. Case-based research by Fang et al. (2022) similarly found that tourism firms with high agility levels during the COVID-19 pandemic benefited from proactive leadership, internal trust, and accelerated innovation adoption. In Morocco, small tourism establishments that embraced digital agility (online booking platforms, remote service delivery) outperformed others in terms of post-crisis recovery (Ministry of Tourism Report, 2023). Thus, agility not only activates deeper capability structures but also provides immediate absorptive and adaptive advantages, particularly in resource-constrained environments such as North African SMEs.

The differentiated effects of industry type and firm characteristics offer key contextual insights. Independent restaurants exhibit significant positive associations with both DC ($\beta = 0.178$, $p = 0.003$) and OR ($\beta = 0.203$, $p = 0.005$), suggesting that autonomy and proximity to decision-

making are instrumental in enhancing adaptive performance. In contrast, hotel-based restaurants demonstrate a negative effect on resilience ($\beta = -0.035$, $p = 0.002$), likely due to centralized structures, reduced operational discretion, and hierarchical inertia. These findings corroborate Prayag et al. (2023), who observe that SMEs with flatter organizational hierarchies and localized autonomy performed more effectively during COVID-related disruptions. Additionally, while firm size shows a positive and significant effect on DC ($\beta = 0.089$, $p = 0.003$) and a marginal influence on OR, firm age does not exhibit any meaningful impact. This supports arguments in the literature (Wang & Ho, 2020) that organizational maturity alone is insufficient for resilience unless it is accompanied by dynamic renewal capabilities. In the Moroccan and broader North African context, these findings emphasize that resilience is not a function of firm scale or legacy, but rather of how flexibly resources are mobilized in the face of volatility.

Conclusion

In the aftermath of the COVID-19 crisis, Moroccan tourism SMEs, particularly in the restaurant segment, have experienced significant disruptions that exposed their structural vulnerabilities and highlighted an urgent need to develop organizational resilience. Conducted within this context, the present study sought to examine the mechanisms through which intangible resources, namely organizational agility (OA) and social capital (SC), contribute to organizational resilience (OR), while also assessing the mediating role of dynamic capabilities (DC). By drawing on the dynamic capabilities theory (Teece, 2007) and the resource-based view (Barney, 1991), the study aimed to offer a contextualized and integrative understanding of how internal and relational capabilities can be strategically mobilized to foster resilience in volatile environments.

The empirical findings provide several compelling insights. First, OA demonstrates a strong and statistically significant direct effect on both SC ($\beta = 0.784$, $p < 0.001$) and OR ($\beta = 0.161$, $p = 0.005$), confirming its dual role as both a relational and adaptive enabler. Second, both OA and SC contribute significantly to resilience through the mediating role of DC (indirect effects: $OA \rightarrow DC \rightarrow OR = 0.285$; $SC \rightarrow DC \rightarrow OR = 0.255$), thereby highlighting the transformative potential of DCs in converting intangible assets into tangible resilience outcomes. Furthermore, firm size was found to positively predict DC ($\beta = 0.089$, $p = 0.003$), while independent restaurants exhibited stronger resilience capacities compared to hotel-based establishments. In

contrast, firm age did not show a significant influence, suggesting that resilience is more dependent on reconfiguration capabilities than on accumulated organizational experience.

- **Theoretical implications**

The study contributes to resilience literature by embedding it in a relational-capabilities framework. It confirms the mediating role of DCs between OA, SC, and OR, extending the applicability of dynamic capabilities theory to tourism SMEs in North Africa. It challenges the RBV's static view by showing that intangible resources require dynamic orchestration to generate impact, and positions OA as a key relational enabler that initiates adaptive learning processes (Ahachmi & al., 2024).

- **Managerial implications**

Practically, the findings highlight the importance of building agility through flexible structures, quick decision-making, and distributed leadership. Strengthening social capital—via stakeholder engagement, trust, and local partnerships—also enhances adaptive capacity. To convert these assets into resilience, firms should institutionalize dynamic routines for sensing, learning, and resource reconfiguration. Institutional actors can support this by promoting digitalization, training, and tailored support for highly adaptive but under-resourced SMEs.

- **Limitations and future research**

Despite its contributions, the study is limited by its cross-sectional design and sector-specific focus, which restrict generalizability. Self-reported data may also introduce bias, and resilience's evolving nature cannot be fully captured in a single time frame. Future research could apply this model to other tourism subsectors and regions across Africa, using longitudinal designs to track resilience over time. Exploring moderating factors such as digital maturity or public policy, and incorporating qualitative methods like case studies, would offer deeper insights into how SMEs build resilience.

Appendixes

Tableau 10: Scale validity and reliability of first order constructs

Latent constructs	Item	Standard loading	t value	VIF value	Skewness	Kurtosis
Structural Capital (CR = 0.856, rA = 0.855, α = 0.855, AVE = 0.633)						
Structural Capital	SC1	0,814	30,888	1,561	-4,021	-2,5
	SC2	0,814	35,528	1,888	-6,02	-1,312
	SC3	0,833	28,585	1,834	-8,152	0,382
	SC4	0,816	38,214	2,146	-5,226	-1,485
	SC5	0,85	38,542	1,848	-6,83	0,618
Relational Capital (CR = 0.883, rA = 0.824, α = 0.815, AVE = 0.585)						
Social Capital Relational Capital (RC)	RC1	0,858	28,508	1,88	-8,304	0,612
	RC2	0,802	32,068	1,886	-8,818	3,32
	RC3	0,862	28,6	1,653	-8,556	3,836
	RC4	0,805	15,638	1,668	-6,543	0,065
	RC5	0,851	32,558	1,865	-5,845	0,281
Cognitive Capital (CR = 0.856, rA = 0.855, α = 0.855, AVE = 0.634)						
Cognitive Capital (CC)	CC1	0,814	38,356	2,014	-6,684	1,884
	CC2	0,851	31,165	1,888	-6,354	1,855
	CC3	0,808	33,023	1,884	-4,35	-0,865
	CC4	0,816	35,055	2,052	-8,852	3,266
	CC5	0,881	25,658	1,688	-5,832	1,43
Organizational Agility (CR = 0.866, rA = 0.868, α = 0.868, AVE = 0.683)						
Organizational Agility (OA)	OA1	0,831	38,51	2,048	-5,811	-0,088
	OA2	0,851	41,848	2,115	-6,123	0,582
	OA3	0,83	46,584	1,858	-8,051	2,052
	OA4	0,836	41,463	2,023	-8,186	1,865
	OA5	0,822	34,556	1,546	-5,016	4,626
	OA6	0,822	32,881	1,546	-5,851	6,454
Sensing Capability (CR = 0.856, rA = 0.861, α = 0.860, AVE = 0.550)						
Sensing Capability (SEC)	SEC1	0,854	35,882	2,058	-5,806	0,104
	SEC2	0,853	25,624	1,814	-6,025	1,352
	SEC3	0,855	38,566	1,53	-8,508	3,101
	SEC4	0,821	43,625	2,138	-6,061	0,656
	SEC5	0,853	23,881	1,852	-6,264	1,252
	SEC6	0,686	21,428	1,456	-5,252	5,245
Seizing Capability (CR = 0.886, rA = 0.811, α = 0.811, AVE = 0.635)						
Dynamic Capability Seizing Capability (SZC)	SZC1	0,883	32,58	1,801	-5,583	0,358
	SZC2	0,841	25,442	1,653	-8,882	2,888
	SZC3	0,8	32,186	1,851	-6,685	2,85
	SZC4	0,85	48,813	2,083	-8,841	2,805
Reconfiguring Capability (CR = 0.883, rA = 0.835, α = 0.834, AVE = 0.601)						
Reconfiguring Capability (RC)	RC1	0,843	23,081	1,528	-8,556	2,452
	RC2	0,814	33,566	1,888	-8,138	1,148
	RC3	0,855	26,538	1,658	-5,853	1,201
	RC4	0,828	32,218	1,811	-5,88	1,041
	RC5	0,816	30,218	1,865	-6,224	1,424
Readiness (CR = 0.852, rA = 0.835, α = 0.835, AVE = 0.685)						
Readiness (RED)	RED1	0,814	33,33	1,881	-6,185	0,833
	RED2	0,84	42,365	1,588	-6,465	2,008
	RED3	0,822	38,018	1,814	-6,455	1,683
	RED4	0,808	32,653	1,855	-5,533	0,323
Response (CR = 0.888, rA = 0.814, α = 0.812, AVE = 0.640)						
Organizational resilience Response (RES)	RES1	0,854	31,15	1,645	-8,85	2,63
	RES2	0,848	22,512	1,48	-5,801	0,553
	RES4	0,846	43,885	1,586	-8,316	2,056
Recovery (CR = 0.855, rA = 0.845, α = 0.844, AVE = 0.682)						
Recovery (REC)	REC1	0,848	55,155	2,084	-8,285	1,508
	REC2	0,818	34,601	1,815	-8,051	4,444
	REC3	0,851	31,438	1,681	-8,4	2,488
	REC4	0,845	43,506	2,025	-8,645	1,888

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